

be attributable to *cis* bonding of ligand molecules in the complexes.

The ir spectra of $[M(AP/AMP)_2(SCN)_2]$ ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}) exhibit a strong and sharp band at 2115-2122 cm^{-1} and weak band at 2085-2100 cm^{-1} (Table 1) attributable to $\nu(C=N)$ stretch of coordinated thiocyanate group¹⁰⁻¹¹. The $\nu(C=S)$ stretching band located near 680-710 cm^{-1} (Table 1)

TABLE-1

Complexes	$\nu(C=N)$ in cm^{-1}	$\nu(C=S)$ in cm^{-1}
$[Pd(AP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2120 s. sp. 2090 w	680 w
$[Pd(AMP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2115 s. sp. 2085 w	710 w
$[Pt(AP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2122 s. sp. 2100 w	705 w
$[Pt(AMP)_2(SCN)_2]$	2118 s. sp. 2090 w	710 w

indicates the S-bonding of thiocyanate group in these thiocyanato complexes^{12,13}. The bonding of thiocyanate group through sulphur atom in complexes is consistent with class 'b' character of Pt(II) and Pd(II).

In the ir spectra of $[M(AP/AMP)_2(NO_2)_2]$ ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}) the $\nu_{as}(NO_2)$ as well as $\nu_s(NO_2)$ vibration is raised to higher frequencies (Table 2)

TABLE-2

Compound	$\nu_{as}(NO_2)$ in cm^{-1}	$\nu_s(NO_2)$ in cm^{-1}	$\delta(ONO)$ in cm^{-1}
$[Pt(AP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1400 vs. br	1305 vs 1268 s	885 s
$[Pt(AMP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1415 s. br	1336 vs 1270 s	890 s
$[Pd(AP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1405 vs. br	1340 s 1275 s	828 s
$[Pd(AMP)_2(NO_2)_2]$	1400 vs. br	1318 s 1282 s	838 s 818 s

vs=very strong; br=broad and s=strong.

suggesting that NO_2 group is coordinated through nitrogen atom in these complexes¹⁴. The $\nu_s(NO_2)$ vibration of the complexes has been found to split into two bands similar to *cis* bonded nitro group in square planar dinitro complexes¹⁵.

Thus, on the basis of above results, it is inferred that in diacido complexes $M(AP/AMP)_2X_2$ ($X = Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_2^- or SCN^- and $M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}), the anions are bonded in *cis* position and ligands are coordinated to metal atom through amino nitrogen as unidentate molecules.

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Molecular Complex of 8-Hydroxyquinoline and Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(II) in Acid Medium

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SAHA and Saha¹ described the molecular complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) and potassium hexacyanoferrates(II and III) respectively prepared in dilute aqueous acetic acid medium; the compositions of the complexes were given as $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2$ oxine and $K_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2$ oxine respectively. A glance at the formulae given raised some doubt in our mind as to what could be the binding forces to make the complexes so stable and we decided to study the first complex independently.

Experimental

All chemicals used in the work were of AnalaR/GR quality. The complex was prepared following the method¹ by dissolving 10.0 g $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ in 30 ml of water and 6.86 g of oxine in 37 ml of dilute (5 M) acetic acid, and mixing the two solution with stirring; the chocolate coloured complex formed immediately was filtered in sintered gooch crucible, washed with water and dried in vacuum desiccator over KOH; yield 9.0 g. No HCN liberated during the preparation of the complex.

Results and Discussion

In contrast to the belief of Saha and Saha, the complex does not contain any appreciable amount of potassium (<0.01%) and does not give the flame test for potassium. This result leads one to believe that the complex is formed between hexacyanoferric(II) acid $[H_4Fe(CN)_6]$ and oxine. To have an

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Idea about the composition of the complex, increasing amounts of oxine solution in 5 M acetic acid were separately added to a fixed amount of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) solution in water so that the oxine/hexacyanoferrate molar ratios varied from one to seven. The complex formed in each case was collected in previously weighed sintered gooch crucible, washed with water, dried in vacuum to constant weight and yield recorded. The results are depicted in the curve A of Fig. 1. The results indicate that the complex has the oxine to hexacyanoferrate(II) ratio 4 : 1. The theoretical yields calculated on the assumption of the composition $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4 \text{ oxine} \cdot 3H_2O$ (which is confirmed later) is shown in the curve B of the same figure. These two curves not only indicate the composition speculated to be reasonable, but also shows that in the preparation of the complex the yield is almost quantitative and not 70% as reported by the previous authors. The reason for 70% yield is presumably due to the use of proportionately less amount of oxine in their preparation.

Fig. 1. A. Yield in g of the complex formed by adding separately varying amounts of 16.3% oxine solution in 5 M acetic acid to 7.50 ml of solution containing 9.18 g of $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ in water. B. Theoretical yield of the complex based on the composition $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4Ox \cdot 3H_2O$ of the complex. C. Conductometric titration of 50.0 mg of the complex by 0.182 N NaOH solution.

Conductometric titration of the complex by alkali was also done to verify the composition derived from the results mentioned. The complex will be acidic with eight protons [four from hexacyanoferrate(II) acid and four from oxine] per molecule. Curve C of Fig. 1 shows the titration curve obtained by titrating a suspension in 30 ml water of 50.0 mg of the complex with 0.182 N NaOH. The titration curve has two breaks at 30 and 59.5 drops (1.29 and 2.59 ml) of alkali, and the equivalent

weight works out to be 107.3, and hence the molecular weight of the complex 858.4 which is very close to 850.7, the calculated molecular weight of the complex. The two breaks at 1 : 1 volume of the alkali also supports the proposed composition of the complex. The non-linear increase in conductance leading to the first break may be due to the different pK_s of $H_4Fe(CN)_6$ as well as to the progressive solubilisation of the complex during the titration. The chocolate colour of the complex vanishes at 30 drops of alkali indicating that with conversion of $H_4Fe(CN)_6$ to $Na_4Fe(CN)_6$ the complex breaks up into the components. The subsequent linear increase leading to the second break reflects the titration of oxine.

Finally, the element analyses results also confirm the formula $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4 \text{ oxine} \cdot 3H_2O$. Found : C, 58.83 ; H, 4.81 ; O, 13.33 ; N, 16.48 ; Fe, 6.63. Calcd. ; C, 59.30 ; H, 4.50 ; O, 13.17 ; N, 16.47 ; Fe, 6.57%. It is to be pointed out that Saha and Saha gave the figures for N (16.75) and Fe (8.54) of which figure for iron is distinctly different from our estimation.

Conclusion : The complex formed between oxine and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) in acidic medium is very similar to potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) with the potassium ions replaced by protonated oxine cations $[OxH^+]$, and the complex should better be represented as $[OxH^+]_4 [Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} \cdot 3H_2O$. The electrostatic binding between the hexacyanoferrate(II) anion and the protonated oxine cations makes this compound stable towards heat. The yield in the preparation of the complex is almost quantitative and hence this may give a potential method of the estimation of oxine or hexacyanoferrate.

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Electromigration of Some Metal Ions on Filter Paper using Aqueous Glycolate Buffer Media

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THE work on separation of metal ions by electromigration on filter paper has been reviewed by Bailey and Yaffe¹ quite adequately. Complexing